

Quantitative structure activity relationship studies on a series of 4-pyridones as antimalarial agents[†]

Basheerulla Shaik^a, Tripti Kaushal^b and Vijay K. Agrawal^{*c}

^aDepartment of Applied Sciences, NITTTR, Shamla Hills, Bhopal-462 002, Madhya Pradesh, India

E-mail : basheerulla.81@gmail.com

^bDepartment of Chemistry, Technocrats Institute of Technology and Science, Bhopal, Madhya Pradesh, India

^cDepartment of Chemistry, A. P. S. University, Rewa-486 003, Madhya Pradesh, India

E-mail : apsvka@yahoo.co.in

Abstract : Quantitative structure-activity relationship (QSAR) studies have been performed on a series of twenty four (24) 4-pyridone analogues as antimalarial agents. A genetic algorithm multiple linear regression (GA-MLR) analysis has shown that three-variable model containing $^2\chi^v$, SpMin8_Bh(s), CATS2D_06_DL, is best for modelling the compounds used in the present study. Using the GA-MLR model, some new compounds have also been proposed which show higher potency.

Keywords : 4-Pyridones, antimalarial activity (pIC₅₀), Quantitative structure-activity relationship study, QSARINS.

Introduction

Malaria is a deadly widespread diseases found in tropical developing countries. Every year about 1.5 to 2.7 million people die due to malaria¹. Moreover, *Plasmodium falciparum* resistant to chloroquine is the main reason for death in this disease. Studies show that chloroquine resistance is also due to a number of mutations in the *pfprt* gene². For chloroquine resistant strains of *P. falciparum* the drug which are available include combination of sulfadoxine and pyrimethamine. However, for the resistance to other antimalarial drugs, atovaquone and proguanil fixed combinations are prescribed for prophylaxis and treatment of malaria. Interestingly gene mutation for cytochrome-b causes resistance to atovaquone. Therefore, proguanil is used in combinations with atovaquone for less or no resistance as well as for synergistic activity.

It has been observed that proguanil is having greater affinity for plasmodial enzyme than the human counterpart, which blocks folate uptake by inhibiting the bacterial dihydrofolate reductase and by blocking the conversion of tetrahydrofolate from dihydrofolate³. Many stu-

dies reveal that 4-pyridones have improved activity against chloroquine-resistant strains as well as atovaquone-resistant *Plasmodium* sp.

Agrawal and co-workers⁴⁻⁹ have successfully modelled the antimalarial activity of some cyclic peroxy acetals, 4-quinolinecarbinolamine antimalarials, substituted phenyl analogues and their Nw-oxides, 2,4-diamino-6-quinazoline sulfonamides, 5-phenoxyprimaquines using topological as well as physico-chemical parameters. They used distance-based topological indices and physico-chemical parameters for modeling the drug activities.

In the recent past topological descriptors have been very successfully used by us in modelling various activities of drug molecules¹⁰⁻¹⁴.

In this study we have tried to model antimalarial activity of 4-pyridones against *P. falciparum* T9-96 strains and used the activity data presented by Yeates and co-workers¹⁵.

Biological activity :

To obtain excellent models with independent variables, the inhibitory activity of 4-pyridones (IC₅₀) against *P. falciparum* T9-96 strain was converted to the negative

[†]In honour of Professor M. C. Chattopadhyaya on the occasion of his 70th birth anniversary.

logarithmic scale (pIC_{50}) for the development of QSAR equations.

Materials and methods :

We have taken a series of 4-pyridones (**1**) that were synthesized and evaluated for their antimalarial activity by Yeates and co-workers¹⁵. This series is listed in Table 1 along with their antimalarial activities (pIC_{50}). The chemical structures were drawn using ChemDoodle software¹⁶. The Table 2 lists the topological parameters of the compounds that were found to govern their potency. These topological parameters used have been calculated using Dragon software¹⁷. In Table 2 we have reported only those parameters which were found to be useful in modelling the activity. They are valence connectivity index of order $-2(^2\chi^v)$, smallest eigenvalue $n. 8$ of Burden matrix weighted by I-state, (SpMin8_Bh(s)), CATS2D Donor-Lipophilic at lag 06 (CATS2D_06_DL).

Results and discussion

Out of 22 compounds listed in Table 1 we have taken

Fig. 1. General structure of 4-pyridones used in the study.

17 compounds for training set and 5 compounds as test set to evaluate the predictability of the developed models. The test set compounds are indicated in the table by a bold superscript 'b'. The QSAR models were obtained using QSARINS software^{18,19}. The generation of training and test sets is done using split option present in QSARINS software by choosing the molecules on random basis. For obtaining QSAR models, Genetic Algorithm-Multi Linear Regression (GA-MLR) was employed using default settings in QSARINS. For statistical validation, variety

Table 1. Series of pyridone derivatives used in the present study

Compd.	X	R ₁	R ₂	Obs. pIC_{50}	Calcd. pIC_{50} from eq. (1)	Calcd. LOO
1	Cl	H	n-C ₈ H ₁₇	5.40	5.48	5.56
2^b	Cl	H		4.96	5.03	-
3^b	Cl	H		5.60	6.19	-
4	Cl	H		7.30	7.28	7.27
5^b	Cl	H		6.40	6.44	-
6	Cl	H		7.22	7.31	7.32
7^b	Br	H		6.82	6.94	-
8	Br	H		7.40	7.27	7.24

Table-1 (contd.)

9 ^b	H	H		6.60	6.74	-
10	Br	H		7.40	7.66	7.70
11	Cl	H		7.52	7.24	7.20
12	Br	H		7.52	7.61	7.62
13	H	H		6.30	6.60	6.71
14	Cl	H		7.22	7.05	7.01
15	Br	H		7.52	7.43	7.40
16	Cl	H		7.52	7.22	7.19
17	Br	H		7.52	7.60	7.61
18	H	H		6.80	6.84	6.85
19	Cl	H		7.52	7.39	7.37
20	Br	H		7.52	7.75	7.79
21	Br	OH		6.53	6.54	6.56
22	H	OH		5.66	5.61	5.57

of statistical parameters were calculated. The best GA-MLR equation based on three descriptors along with statistical parameters were as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{pIC}_{50} = & 0.9383 (\pm 0.2265) {}^2\chi^v - 3.4832 \\ & (\pm 2.3689) \text{SpMin8_Bh(s)} - 0.6144 \\ & (\pm 0.1496) \text{CATS2D_06_DL} + 1.7642 \quad (1) \end{aligned}$$

$N = 17$, $R^2_{\text{tr}} = 0.935$, $R^2_{\text{adj.}} = 0.919$, $S = 0.194$, $F = 61.850$, $K_{\text{xx}} = 0.048$, $\Delta K = 0.291$, $RMSE_{\text{tr}} = 0.170$, $MAE_{\text{tr}} = 0.139$, $RSS_{\text{tr}} = 0.488$, $CCC_{\text{tr}} = 0.966$.

$Q^2_{\text{LOO}} = 0.904$, $RMSE_{\text{cv}} = 0.205$, $MAE_{\text{cv}} = 0.172$, $PRESS_{\text{cv}} = 0.717$, $CCC_{\text{cv}} = 0.949$, $Q^2_{\text{LMO}} = 0.866$, $R^2_{Y_{\text{scr}}} = 0.193$, $Q^2_{Y_{\text{scr}}} = -0.449$, $R^2_{\text{Pred}} = 0.916$, $RMSE_{\text{ext}} = 0.277$, $MAE_{\text{ext}} = 0.191$, $PRESS_{\text{ext}} = 0.385$, $CCC_{\text{ext}} = 0.920$, $R^2_{\text{m}\Delta} = 0.082$, $R^2_{\text{m}} = 0.855$.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{pIC}_{50} = & 0.9552 (\pm 0.2884) {}^2\chi^v - 0.6164 \\ & (\pm 0.1907) \text{CATS2D_06_DL} + 1.1197 \quad (2) \end{aligned}$$

$N = 17$, $R^2_{\text{tr}} = 0.884$, $R^2_{\text{adj.}} = 0.867$, $S = 0.249$, $F = 53.1917$, $K_{\text{xx}} = 0.074$, $\Delta K = 0.432$, $RMSE_{\text{tr}} = 0.226$, $MAE_{\text{tr}} = 0.183$, $RSS_{\text{tr}} = 0.867$, $CCC_{\text{tr}} = 0.938$.

Table 2. Values of the calculated descriptors along with their activity values

Compd.	${}^2\chi^v$	SpMin8_Bh(s)	CATS2D_06_DL
1	5.392	0.208	1
2	4.137	0	1
3	4.714	0	0
4	7.346	0.218	1
5	6.292	0.177	1
6	6.288	0.103	0
7	6.126	0.163	0
8	6.266	0.108	0
9	5.833	0.144	0
10	6.703	0.114	0
11	6.291	0.124	0
12	6.706	0.128	0
13	5.965	0.218	0
14	6.420	0.213	0
15	6.835	0.215	0
16	6.423	0.165	0
17	6.838	0.168	0
18	5.962	0.148	0
19	6.417	0.113	0
20	6.832	0.122	0
21	6.811	0.110	2
22	5.939	0.142	2

$Q^2_{\text{LOO}} = 0.823$, $RMSE_{\text{cv}} = 0.278$, $MAE_{\text{cv}} = 0.228$, $PRESS_{\text{cv}} = 1.320$, $CCC_{\text{cv}} = 0.906$, $Q^2_{\text{LMO}} = 0.787$, $R^2_{Y_{\text{scr}}} = 0.128$, $Q^2_{Y_{\text{scr}}} = -0.340$, $R^2_{\text{Pred}} = 0.985$, $RMSE_{\text{ext}} = 0.244$, $MAE_{\text{ext}} = 0.177$, $PRESS_{\text{ext}} = 0.299$, $CCC_{\text{ext}} = 0.55$, $R^2_{\text{m}\Delta} = 0.092$, $R^2_{\text{m}} = 0.705$.

$$\text{pIC}_{50} = 1.0242 (\pm 0.5814) {}^2\chi^v + 0.4580 \quad (3)$$

$N = 17$, $R^2_{\text{tr}} = 0.484$, $R^2_{\text{adj.}} = 0.450$, $S = 0.506$, $F = 14.100$, $K_{\text{xx}} = 0.000$, $\Delta K = 0.696$, $RMSE_{\text{tr}} = 0.475$, $MAE_{\text{tr}} = 0.390$, $RSS_{\text{tr}} = 3.846$, $CCC_{\text{tr}} = 0.653$.

$Q^2_{\text{LOO}} = 0.260$, $RMSE_{\text{cv}} = 0.569$, $MAE_{\text{cv}} = 0.458$, $PRESS_{\text{cv}} = 5.521$, $CCC_{\text{cv}} = 0.500$, $Q^2_{\text{LMO}} = 0.205$, $R^2_{Y_{\text{scr}}} = 0.060$, $Q^2_{Y_{\text{scr}}} = -0.217$, $R^2_{\text{Pred}} = 0.906$, $RMSE_{\text{ext}} = 0.302$, $MAE_{\text{ext}} = 0.267$, $PRESS_{\text{ext}} = 457$, $CCC_{\text{ext}} = 0.926$, $R^2_{\text{m}\Delta} = 0.134$, $R^2_{\text{m}} = 0.696$.

Among the statistical parameters, N is the number of data points (compounds), R^2_{tr} is the correlation coefficient of training set compounds, Q^2_{LOO} is the square of the cross-validated correlation coefficient obtained from leave-one-out (LOO), S is the standard deviation, F is Fischer ratio between the variances of calculated and observed activities. The remaining symbols have their usual meanings²⁰.

Of the above four models, the very first model [eq. (1)] is found to be statistically most significant. The validation of model using different statistical parameters indicated that the model is free from the defect of chance. In models 1-3, the descriptors ${}^2\chi^v$, which is a connectivity index descriptor, has positive coefficient meaning that the second order valance connectivity index is favouring the activity. Similarly, the negative coefficient of SpMin8_Bh(s), CATS2D_06_DL indicated that the molecule will have adverse effect towards activity. Thus, we conclude that the activity of the compounds is governed by their properties. All the parameters used in the proposed models appeared to be significant, as if they are removed one by one the significance level of the model decreases [eqs. (1)-(3)].

The average r^2_{m} and Δr^2_{m} were calculated for judging the quality of the proposed model using r^2_{m} metric method. It is well established that for an acceptable QSAR model the value of average r^2_{m} should be > 0.5 and Δr^2_{m} should be < 0.2 ^{21,22}. In our study two different variants of this parameter, r^2_{m} and Δr^2_{m} , were calculated. A close observation of this eq. (1) clearly indicates that the values r^2_{m}

Shaik *et al.* : Quantitative structure activity relationship studies on a series of 4-pyridones as antimalarial agents

and Δr^2_m obtained from the r^2_m metrics are in favour of the three-parametric model proposed by us.

Randomization test is performed to investigate the probability of chance correlation for the best models. Generally in randomization test the dependent variable (pIC_{50}) is randomly shuffled and new QSAR models are investigated using the original descriptors. After performing the test, the results indicate that the coefficient of determination obtained by chance is low while the RMSE values are high. This clearly indicates that the models obtained in this study are better than those obtained by chance.

The model expressed by eq. (1) was found to have good predictive ability when the activities of both the training and test set compounds were compared with their corresponding observed activities. A graph between calculated and observed activities also verify this fact (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2.

Using eq. (1), we have proposed 5 compounds in the series mentioned in Table 1. The activity of proposed compounds are found better theoretically. Thus, all pre-

Table 3. Some proposed compounds belonging to the series and their predicted activity

Compd.	X	R ₁	R ₂	$^2\chi^v$	SpMin8_Bh(s)	CATS2D_06_DL	Pred. pIC_{50}
1	Br		6.86	0.00	0.00	8.20	
2	Cl		6.44	0.00	0.00	7.81	
3	Cl		6.44	0.00	0.00	7.81	
4	Br		6.86	0.00	0.00	8.20	
5	Br		6.82	0.00	0.00	8.16	

dicted compounds were listed in Table 3 and these can be synthesized and tested for actual drug activity.

The Lipinski's parameters of these proposed compounds were also evaluated which are shown in Table 4. This table shows that all compounds fulfill Lipinski's conditions, according to which potential drugs are less likely to face any problem of absorption and permeability

Table 4. Data related to Lipinski rules and ADME/T values of predicted compounds

Compd.	MW	log P	HD	HA
1	433.319	3.221	1	3
2	388.868	3.137	1	3
3	388.868	3.137	1	3
4	433.319	3.221	1	3
5	434.307	2.070	1	4

if they fulfill four of the five conditions, namely their molecular weight (MW) is not more than 500, log P is not more than 5, number of H-bond donors (HDs) is not more than 5, and number of H-bond acceptors (HAs) is not more than 10.

Conclusion

On the basis of the obtained results we have made the following conclusions. The best model obtained suggests that the $^2\chi^v$, Burden eigenvalues and CATS2D_06_DL play important role in prediction of biological activity of present set of compounds.

(i) Positive coefficient of $^2\chi^v$ suggests that second order valance connectivity indices plays a dominant role in deciding the antimalarial activity of present set of compounds. Therefore in designing the new compounds the structure be modified in such a way so as to get a higher value of $^2\chi^v$.

(ii) Both Burden Eigen values and CATS2D_06_DL have negative coefficients, therefore molecules having low value of Burden Eigen values and CATS2D_06_DL should be preferred in designing new compounds to get better activity.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors Dr. Basheerulla Shaik is thankful to Paola Gramatica for providing the copy of QSARINS software.

References

1. K. Park, "Preventive and social medicine", (Ed. 15), BanarsidasBhanot, India, 1997.
2. Wilson and Gisvold's, "Textbook of Organic Medicinal and Pharmaceutical Chemistry", (Ed. 11), Lipincott Williams & Wilkins, Philadelphia, 2004, 288.
3. H. P. Rang, M. M. Dale, J. M. Ritter and P. K. Moore, "Pharmacology", Churchill Livingstone, Edinburgh, 2003.
4. B. Shaik, J. Singh and V. K. Agrawal, *Med. Chem. Res.*, 2012, **21**, 2097.
5. V. K. Agrawal and P. V. Khadikar, *Oxid. Commun.*, 2003, **26**, 179.
6. V. K. Agrawal, S. Sinha, S. Bano and P. V. Khadikar, *Pol. J. Pharmacol.*, 1999, **51**, 517.
7. V. K. Agrawal, S. Sinha, S. Bano and P. V. Khadikar, *Acta Microbiol. Immunol. Hung.*, 2001, **48**, 17.
8. V. K. Agrawal, R. Srivastava and P. V. Khadikar, *Bioorg. Med. Chem.*, 2001, **9**, 3287.
9. V. K. Agrawal, R. Sharma and P. V. Khadikar, *Oxid. Commun.*, 2003, **26**, 186.
10. K. Anitha, N. Singh, B. Shaik, I. Ahmad, V. K. Agrawal and S. P. Gupta, *J. Modern Med. Chem.*, 2015, **3**, 49.
11. J. Singh, B. Shaik, V. K. Agrawal and P. V. Khadikar, *Interdiscip. Sci. Comput. Life Sci.*, 2012, **4**, 215.
12. O. Deeb, B. Shaik and V. K. Agrawal, *J. Enzy. Inhib. Med. Chem.*, 2014, **5**, 670.
13. B. Shaik, T. Zafar and V. K. Agrawal. *Int. J. Med. Chem.*, 2013, 1.
14. K. Anita, V. K. Agrawal, B. Shaik and S. Sharma, *Int. J. Pharm. Sci. Res.*, 2014, **5**, 1000.
15. C. L. Yeates, J. F. Batchelor, E. C. Capon, N. J. Cheesman, M. Fry, A. T. Hudson, M. Pudney, H. Trimming, J. Woolven, J. M. Bueno, J. Chicharro, E. Fernández, J. M. Fiandor, D. Gargallo-Viola, F. G. de las. Heras, E. Herrerros and M. L. León, *J. Med. Chem.*, 2008, **51**, 2845.
16. <http://www.chemdoodle.com>
17. Talete SRL, Dragon (Software for Molecular Descriptor Calculation) Version 6.0 - 2013 - <http://www.talete.mi.it/>
18. P. Gramatica, N. Chirico, E. Papa, S. Cassani and S. Kovarich, *J. Comput. Chem.*, 2013, **34**, 2121.
19. P. Gramatica, S. Cassani and N. Chirico, *J. Comput. Chem.*, 2014, **35**, 1036.
20. N. Chirico and P. Gramatica, *J. Comput. Chem.*, 2011, **51**, 2320.
21. K. Roy, P. Chakraborty, I. Mitra, P. K. Ojha, S. Kar and R. N. Das, *J. Chem. Inf. Comput. Sci.*, 2013, **34**, 1071.
22. A. Golbraikh and A. Tropsha, *J. Mol. Graph. Model.*, 2002, **20**, 269.